

NOTES

TABLE 1—INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF HETEROPOLY COMPOUNDS

(NH ₄) ₁₀ [MoV ₁₂ O ₃₈]20H ₂ O	3480b 3140b	1615m	1400s	935s 915s	800s 715s	560s 410m
Ignited sample (400°)	—	—	—	910s 890s	—	—
(NH ₄) ₈ [WV ₆ O ₁₈]11H ₂ O	3445b 3170b	1605b	1405b	975s 980s	840b 755m	600s 410s
Ignited sample (350°)	—	—	—	910s 940s	—	—
K ₂ [MoV ₆ O ₁₈]11H ₂ O	3440s	1610m	—	940s	805s 720s	580s
Ignited sample (350°)	—	—	—	910s	—	—
(NH ₄) ₄ [CoV ₁₀ O ₃₀]18H ₂ O	3180b	1615m	1410m	960s	850b 780b	600b 442b
Ignited sample (400°)	—	—	—	980	—	442s
(NH ₄) ₇ [SbV ₁₂ O ₃₆]28H ₂ O	3485b 3175b	—	1890s	1000s 975s	745s	600s 455m
Ignited sample (450°)	—	—	—	915s 945s	—	—

s = sharp, m = medium, b = broad.

samples were also taken. The decomposition temperature of the heteropoly complexes was taken as the ignition temperature. The peaks, characteristic of lattice water as well as ammonium ion were not found. The observed peaks confirmed the breakage of heteropoly complexes into the lower oxides of their constituent atoms.

Potential Local Anaesthetic Agents. Part-III :
Alkylaryl aminoacetyl-2-aminothiazoles
and Benzimidazoles

J. S. UPADHYAYA*, P. K. SRIVASTAVA
and

R. D. SHARMA (LATE)

Surgical Research Laboratories, Institute of Medical Sciences,
Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 6 February 1981, revised 1 December 1981,
accepted 7 June 1982

References

1. S. K. ROY and P. P. JHA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, **19A**, 919.
2. G. C. BHATTACHARYA and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1027.
3. S. K. ROY and P. P. JHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1027.
4. S. K. ROY and P. P. JHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 232.
5. A. PERLOFF, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 2228.
6. C. M. FLYNN and M. T. POPE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 85.
7. C. DUVAL, "Inorganic Thermogravimetric Analysis", Elsevier Publishing Company, Amsterdam, London, New York, 1968, p. 245.
8. G. A. TSIGDINOS and C. J. HALLADA, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 487.
9. D. H. BROWN, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1962, **19**, 585.
10. N. E. SHARPLESS and J. S. MUNDAY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, **29**, 1619.
11. P. J. LUCCHESI and W. A. GRASSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 1847.
12. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, 1968, p. 107.
13. J. VANDER ELSEN and D. W. ROBINSON, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1961, **17**, 1249.
14. J. W. WADDINGTON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4340.
15. K. NAKAMOTO, Y. MORIMOTO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4583.
16. H. STEBERT, *Z. Anorg. Allgem. Chem.*, 1954, **275**, 325.
17. G. A. TSIGDINOS, "Heteropoly Compounds", Method Chim (Eng. Edn.), Academic Press, New York, 1976, Vol 8, Chap. 82.
18. J. FUJITA, A. E. MARTELL and K. NAKAMOTO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **36**, 324, 331.

THE essential structural requirements for anaestheticophore group in local anaesthetics seems to be a lipophilic moiety containing an aromatic nucleus, an intermediate alkyl or aryl substituted chain and a hydrophilic end consisting of a tertiary amino group¹⁻⁴. The thiazole and imidazole groups are of great importance in biological systems⁵⁻¹⁰. The title compounds appear to possess all the necessary structural requirements for local anaesthetic agent. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise some alkylaryl-aminoacetyl-2-aminothiazoles and benzimidazoles by the condensation of chloroacetylchloride with 2-aminothiazole/benzimidazole followed by treatment with various primary and secondary amines.

The structures of these compounds have been established on the basis of their analysis and infrared spectrum. IR spectra of these compounds show characteristic strong absorption peaks at 1650-1625 cm⁻¹ and 1370-1360 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C=O and C-N bands, respectively. An

*Author for correspondences, Present Address : Institute of Paper Technology, (University of Roorkee), Saharanpur-247 001.

absorption band at 3200-3150 cm⁻¹ indicates the NH stretching frequency. A strong absorption peak in the region 1700-1670 cm⁻¹ is attributed to secondary amide band.

Experimental

Chloroacetyl-2-aminothiazole/benzimidazole were prepared by known methods².

Preparation of dimethylaminoacetyl-2-aminothiazole / N-methylanilinoacetyl-2-aminobenzimidazole : Equimolar quantities of dimethylamine/N-methylaniline and chloroacetyl-2-aminothiazole/chloroacetyl-2-aminobenzimidazole in ethanol were mixed together with constant stirring. After the addition, the reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 hr and the excess of ethanol was distilled off. Residue, on washing with sodium bicarbonate and crystallisation from dilute ethanol afforded the title compounds. The homogeneity of these compounds were tested by tlc studies. The percentage yield and melting point of the compounds are reported in Table 1.

These bases were converted into the corresponding hydrochlorides by passing dry hydrogen chloride gas in ethereal solution.

Adopting a similar procedure, various alkylarylamine acetyl-2-aminothiazoles and benzimidazoles have been prepared by the condensation of chloroacetyl-2-aminothiazole/chloroacetyl-2-aminobenzimidazole with different amines.

Biological screening results : The compounds prepared were investigated for their local anaesthetic activity—surface anaesthesia in rabbit cornea¹¹, infiltration anaesthesia in guineapig¹² and conduction anaesthesia¹³ on frog (*Rana tigrina*). The results of preliminary studies are recorded in Table 2. Procaine hydrochloride was used as the standard drug. The screening results indicate that all the compounds except compounds no. 2, 6, 10 and 14 were moderately active when tested as surface anaesthetic at concentration 2 to 2.5% in 0.7% saline. However, compounds no. 1, 4, 5, 11, 13 and 14 were found to be inactive when tested as infiltration anaesthetic at the same concentration, whereas compounds no. 17 and 18 showed

TABLE 1—ALKYLARYLAMINOACETYL-2-AMINOTHIAZOLES AND ALKYLARYLAMINOACETYL-2-AMINO BENZIMIDAZOLES

Sl. No.	Compounds*		Yield %	m.p. °C	Formula	Hydrochloride m.p. °C
	X	R ₁ (or H) R ₂				
1.		Diallyl	75	130	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS	215-17
2.	"	Dimethyl	70	138	C ₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS	189-91
3.	"	Diisopropyl	65	118	C ₁₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ OS	185-87
4.	"	N-methylanilino	70	90	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS	213-15
5.	"	Pyridyl	75	106	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ OS	221-22
6.	"	Pyrimidino	60	135	C ₈ H ₈ N ₂ OS	192-94
7.	"	N,N-dimethyl anilino-p	75	82	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	201-03
8.	"	Piperidino	70	87	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	224-25
9.	"	Piperizino	68	65	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS	205-07
10.	"	Morpholino	60	70	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	195-97
11.		Diallyl	80	120	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	185-87
12.	"	Dimethyl	75	125	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O	241-42
13.	"	Diisopropyl	68	107	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₄ O	233-35
14.	"	N-methylaniline	65	98	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O	197-99
15.	"	Pyridyl	76	92	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O	203-05
16.	"	Pyrimidino	60	85	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ O	217-19
17.	"	N,N-dimethyl-anilino-p	68	101	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	235-37
18.	"	Piperidino	70	135	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	176-77
19.	"	Piperizino	75	117	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₄ O	187-89
20.	"	Morpholino	62	79	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	179-81

* Elemental analyses results for C, H, N and S for these compounds are within ±0.5% of the theoretical values.

NOTES

TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL SCREENING RESULTS OF ALKYLARYLAMINOACETYL-2-AMINOTHIAZOLES AND ALKYLARYLAMINOACETYL-2-AMINOBENZIMIDAZOLES AS LOCAL ANAESTHETIC

Compound No.	Surface anaesthesia			Infiltration anaesthesia			Conduction anaesthesia			
	Conc. of drug (%)	Intensity	Duration (min)	Conc. of drug (%)	Intensity	Duration (min)	Conc. of drug (%)	Onset of anaesthesia (min) in HCl of strength		
								0.5 N	0.1 N	0.2 N
1.	2	complete	3	0.2	nil	—	0.2	20	21	21
2.	2	nil	—	0.2	partial	8	—	—	—	—
3.	—	—	—	—	complete	10	0.2	18	19	19
4.	2.5	partial	8	0.2	complete	15	0.2	8	9	10
5.	2	complete	10	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
6.	2	complete	14	0.2	nil	—	0.2	15	16	17
7.	2	partial	6	0.2	nil	—	0.2	20	20	21
8.	2.5	complete	8	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
9.	2	nil	—	0.2	complete	9	0.2	23	24	24
10.	2	complete	22	0.2	complete	16	0.2	9	10	10
11.	2	complete	18	0.2	partial	5	0.2	13	15	16
12.	—	—	—	0.25	complete	7	—	—	—	—
13.	2	partial	12	0.2	complete	12	0.2	10	11	12
14.	2.5	complete	14	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
15.	2	nil	—	0.2	complete	8	0.2	5	6	7
16.	2	complete	4	0.2	nil	—	0.2	17	18	19
17.	2	partial	4	0.2	complete	3	0.2	20	22	22
18.	2.5	complete	5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
19.	2	complete	7	0.2	nil	—	0.2	9	10	10
20.	2	nil	—	0.1	nil	—	0.2	19	20	20
Procaine hydrochloride (Standard)	2	—	—	0.2	nil	—	—	—	—	—
	2	partial	2	0.1	partial	4	0.2	27	29	29
	2.5	complete	4	0.2	complete	6	—	—	—	—
	2	complete	8	0.2	complete	5	0.2	31	32	33
	2	complete	20	0.2	complete	37	0.2	7	8	8
	2	complete	19	0.2	complete	20	0.2	10	11	12
	2	complete	13	0.1	partial	10	0.2	12	13	13
	2.5	complete	15	0.2	complete	12	—	—	—	—
	2	complete	10	0.2	complete	10	0.2	16	17	17
	2	complete	15	0.2	complete	12	0.2	15	16	17

maximum activity with duration of infiltration anaesthesia on frog. Compounds no 7, 8, 17 and 18 were found to be more active than the standard drug when tested as surface anaesthetic. In comparison to the standard drug, the compounds no. 4 and 20 were found to be equally active, compounds no. 1, 2, 5, 6, 11, 12 and 14 slightly more active and compounds no. 15 and 16 were observed to be most active.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. F. F. BLICKE and H. C. PARK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 1200.
2. A. M. MATTOCKS and O. S. HUTCHINSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3474.
3. P. N. BHARGAVA and G. C. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 77.
4. N. LOFGREN, *Ark. Kem. Min. Geol.*, 1946, **22A** nr, 18; *Chem. Abs.*, 1949, **43**, 1021.
5. P. K. SRIVASTAVA and P. N. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 304, 977.
6. J. S. UPADHYAYA, P. K. SRIVASTAVA and R. D. SHARMA, *Ind. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1977, **39**, 56.

7. J. S. UPADHYAYA, S. P. SRIVASTAVA and M. P. SHARMA, *Ind. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1980, **42**, 88.
8. J. S. UPADHYAYA, *Ind. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1980, **42**, 133.
9. J. S. UPADHYAYA and P. K. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 789.
10. I. A. KAYE, T. VITALI and BALLOWITZ, in a review on "The Design of Local Anaesthetic" in "Drug Design", (Ed.) Ariens, Vol. III, Chap. 6, p. 288.
11. T. SOLLMANN, *J. Pharmacol.*, 1918, **11**, 17.
12. E. BULBRING and I. WAJDA, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 1945, **85**, 78.

Studies on Antitubercular Agents. Part-III : Preparation of Some *p*-(2,4-Diaryl-amino-6-S-Triazinylamino)-Benzaldehyde/ Acetophenone Thiosemicarbazones as Potential Tuberculostatic Agents

N. A. LANGALIA and K. A. THAKER

University Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar-364 002

Manuscript received 9 June 1981, revised 19 December 1981, accepted 1 May 1982

LITERATURE reveals that a number of studies have been carried out on the antileprotic and antitubercular activity of thiosemicarba-